

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of Halogenonitrophenyl Esters of N-(propyl, dipropyl, cyclopentyl and dicyclohexyl) Dithioformic Acids

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A few halogenonitrophenyl esters of N-(propyl, dipropyl, cyclopentyl and dicyclohexyl) dithioformic acids have been prepared and screened for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum* and *Pyricularia oryzae*. They were found to possess significant antifungal activity.

A large number of dithiocarbamates¹ have been known to be potent fungicides. Recently Sen Gupta *et al* have reported the synthesis and insecticidal activity of several new dithiocarbamates². The ability of some halogenonitrophenyl and naphthyl esters of piperidino and morpholino-dithiocarbamic acids³ to exhibit fungicidal activity prompted us to synthesise the title compounds. These were also screened for their antifungal activity.

Experimental

Sodium salt of N-substituted Dithioformic Acid :

A solution of amine (0.01M) in methanol (25 ml) was added with stirring to an ice cold solution of sodium hydroxide (0.01M) in water (10 ml) with vigorous shaking and maintaining the temperature below 5°. The mixture was then stirred for another one hour below 10°. The product was filtered and crystallised from methanol to give colourless crystals.

Halogenonitrophenyl Esters of N-substituted Dithioformic Acid :

A solution of halogenonitrobenzene (0.01M) in ethanol was added dropwise with stirring to a 10% solution of sodium salt of N-substituted dithioformic acid in ethyl alcohol keeping the temperature below 5°. The reaction mixture was stirred until the product separated. The ester was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol. The structure of these compounds was supported by infrared spectra.

The infra-red spectra of some of these compounds have been recorded in solid state by KBr technique. The I.R. spectra of these esters show a sharp band, around 1642-1480 cm⁻¹ characteristic of C=N, partial double bond. The C=N stretching in these compounds is shortened under the influence of conical form such as :—

due to the influence of second sulphur atom. The stretching frequencies of C=C in benzene derivatives indicated in the range 1520–1480 cm⁻¹ and 16.0–15.0 cm⁻¹ respectively, indicate the presence of a benzene nucleus. Their melting points and analytical data are recorded in Tables 1 to 4.

TABLE 1—ESTER OF N-PROPYL DITHIOFORMIC ACIDS

Sr. No.	R ₁ , R ₂ , R ₃ , R ₄ , R ₅					M.P. °C	AT	Ed50 ppm	
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅			HS	PO
1.	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	H	H	1200	37	33	39
2.	NO ₂	H	H	H	NO ₂	155	37	30	37
3.	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	65	25	37	30
4.	Cl	H	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	80	45	50	55
5.	H	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	98	72	64	62
6.	NO ₂	H	Cl	H	NO ₂	100	50	60	50
7.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	87	210	200	164
8.	NO ₂	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	113	200	180	210
9.	Cl	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	145	64	63	200
10.	Cl	H	NO ₂	CH ₃	NO ₂	168	164	210	180
11.	CH ₃	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	112	200	250	210
12.	NO ₂	CH ₃	Cl	H	NO ₂	103	150	160	135

TABLE 2—ESTERS OF N-DIPROPYL DITHIOFORMIC ACIDS

Sr. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M.P. °C	Ed50 ppm		
							AT	HS	PO
1.	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	H	H	90	35	33	33
2.	NO ₂	H	H	H	NO ₂	100	33	30	35
3.	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	74	30	32	30
4.	Cl	H	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	115	35	37	37
5.	H	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	125	62	65	60
6.	NO ₂	H	Cl	H	NO ₂	92	45	47	42
7.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	80	160	165	158
8.	NO ₂	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	110	175	200	160
9.	NO ₂	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	147	66	60	62
10.	Cl	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	150	210	200	180
11.	Cl	H	NO ₂	CH ₃	NO ₂	127	180	165	167
12.	CH ₃	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	109	150	160	135

TABLE 3—ESTERS OF N-CYCLOPHENYL DITHIOFORMIC ACIDS

Sr. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M.P. °C	Ed50 ppm		
							AT	HS	PO
1.	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	H	H	201	50	52	55
2.	NO ₂	H	H	H	NO ₂	114	45	50	50
3.	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	130	40	42	50
4.	Cl	H	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	125	50	55	60
5.	H	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	150	80	75	90
6.	NO ₂	H	Cl	H	NO ₂	128	68	65	70
7.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	95	100	120	98
8.	NO ₂	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	118	90	80	102
9.	Cl	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	102	78	68	70
10.	Cl	H	NO ₂	CH ₃	NO ₂	175	200	210	180
11.	CH ₃	Cl	NO ₂	CH ₃	NO ₂	115	41	300	250
12.	NO ₂	CH ₃	Cl	H	NO ₂	110	210	200	200

TABLE 4—ESTERS OF DICYCLOHEXYL-DITHIOFORMIC ACIDS

Sr. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	M.P. °C	Ed50 ppm		
							AT	HS	PO
1.	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	H	H	72	54	46	54
2.	NO ₂	H	H	H	NO ₂	101	52	50	45
3.	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	66	35	50	38
4.	Cl	H	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	130	53	55	65
5.	H	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	176	100	90	98
6.	NO ₂	H	Cl	H	NO ₂	96	50	52	45
7.	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	95	200	250	220
8.	NO ₂	H	CH ₃	H	NO ₂	105	200	90	98
9.	Cl	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	99	90	100	150
10.	Cl	H	NO ₂	CH ₃	NO ₂	121	280	300	450
11.	CH ₃	Cl	NO ₂	H	NO ₂	119	400	500	410
12.	NO ₂	CH ₃	Cl	H	NO ₂	165	250	200	220

Screening Results : These compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum* and *Pyricularia oryzae* by spore germination method⁴. The dosages in ppm required for the inhibition of 50% growth of fungi have been recorded (Tables 1 to 4).

The fungitoxicity of the esters of N-substituted dithioformic acids depends upon both the ester and the dithioformate moiety. In the ester moiety the fungitoxicity increases sharply when halogen atom or nitro group are placed at ortho or para position in the phenyl ring. However, a halogen atom at meta position seems to decrease fungitoxicity. The effect of methyl group is rather abnormal, when present at ortho or meta position in the phenyl ring of the ester moiety it decreases fungitoxicity. However, when present at the para position the fungitoxicity increases.

In the dithioformate moiety, the presence of lower alkyl groups increases the toxicity. As the number of carbon atom increases the activity decreases. In these compounds, fungitoxicity falls rapidly in the following

order :

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